

Ancient Medicine in Modern Times: Exploring Traditional Medicine Usage for Childhood Illnesses in Karu, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: The World Health Organization estimates that over 80% of people in developing regions of Africa and Asia rely primarily on traditional medicine for their healthcare needs. Despite World Health Organization's warnings about potential risks, especially among children, traditional medicine remains widely used, often without adequate scientific scrutiny. This study explored the practices and perceptions of mothers of children aged 0–5 years in Karu, Nasarawa State, Nigeria, regarding the use of traditional medicine.

Methods: In-depth interviews were conducted with 13 mothers of children under five years of age to collect qualitative data on their experiences using traditional medicine for childhood illnesses. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze demographic data via the SPSS statistics, while qualitative responses were transcribed, coded, and analyzed thematically.

Results: Fever and *jedi-jedi* emerged as the most common childhood ailments treated with traditional medicine. Key drivers of traditional medicine use included perceived effectiveness, affordability, availability, and cultural familiarity. Remedies were administered in various forms: liquid, solid, powder, and oil; through oral, anal, or topical routes depending on the condition being treated.

Conclusion: Most respondents felt confident in the safety and efficacy of traditional medicines for young children, with minimal concern about side effects. These findings highlight the need to better understand the persistent reliance on traditional medicine in paediatric care and call for further research to ensure its safe and informed integration into healthcare systems.

Key Words: Traditional Medicine, Child Health, Health seeking behaviour

Introduction

Traditional medicine has been the cornerstone of healthcare across cultures for thousands of years. Its earliest documented use dates back over 5,000 years to the Sumerian civilization of southern Mesopotamia with similar evidence found in the Egyptian *Ebers Papyrus* of 1552 BC. In ancient India, herbalists like Charaka and Sushruta cataloged medicinal plants and practices that have persisted through centuries, evolving in response to pandemics, wars, environmental changes, and sociocultural shifts.¹ In colonial America, women employed remedies such as cupping and leeching to manage ailments like malaria, goiter, and dysentery. These practices were rooted in herbal traditions that extended into the 19th and 20th centuries.² Traditional medicine is not limited to minor ailments; it encompasses diagnostic rituals, mental health therapy, childbirth support, and surgical procedures such as tribal mark incisions, tooth extraction, and circumcision.³ As such, the study of traditional medicine is inherently complex and deeply embedded in cultural, religious, and historical contexts.

The World Health Organization (WHO), through the 1978 Alma Ata Declaration, formally recognized the role of traditional medicine in achieving global health targets. It defines traditional medicine as the “knowledge, skills, and practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences indigenous to different cultures, used in the maintenance of health and the prevention, diagnosis, improvement or treatment of physical and mental illness.”⁴ Other scholars describe it as a combination of plant, animal, and mineral-based medicines, spiritual therapies, and manual techniques used to treat illness or promote wellness.^{4,5} These treatments may take various forms, including animal extracts, oils, powders, liquids, and tree bark.⁵

Globally, traditional medicine plays a dual role: it is a health resource and a sociocultural asset. It has been integrated into biomedical systems, adapted to technological changes, and sustained by strong community trust.⁶ In many parts of the world, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, it serves as the first point of care. During public health crises such as the COVID-19, traditional treatments were often turned to when biomedical

solutions were uncertain or delayed.⁷ The reasons for using traditional medicine are multifaceted. Motivation includes cultural beliefs, affordability, perceived illness severity, and guidance from trusted community sources.⁸ Lower education levels, older age, anxiety, depression, and multiple chronic conditions are also associated with increased usage of traditional medicine.⁹

In Africa, and particularly Nigeria, traditional medicine remains a crucial part of healthcare. The WHO has noted that up to 80% of the population in some African and Asian countries rely on traditional remedies for their primary healthcare needs.² However, concerns persist over inappropriate or unregulated use. Some traditional medicines contain bioactive compounds that, if taken in large quantities, can lead to serious health complications including liver damage, renal failure, and gastrointestinal problems.¹⁰ Although herbal therapies have therapeutic potential, excessive or incorrect use can render otherwise safe substances toxic.^{10,11}

In Nigeria, studies have consistently shown high rates of traditional medicine usage across different regions. In Ekiti State, for example, 85% of respondents had used herbal medicines within two years, mainly citing effectiveness (39.6%) and affordability (31.9%).¹² Similarly, in Jos South, Plateau State, 83.7% used traditional medicine for malaria and fever, with 80.6% recommending continued use.¹³ These preferences are shaped by religion, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status. A study found that women with higher education and those from Ibo and Hausa ethnic groups were less likely to use traditional medicine compared to their Yoruba counterparts.¹⁴ Even among biomedical professionals, usage is notable. A study found that 85.9% of pharmacists had used traditional medicine at least once, with 21.3% being current users.¹⁵ While many used it for general wellness, they expressed concern about lack of safety and regulatory oversight.

A study among staff and students of the University of Nigeria Nsukka revealed that over 70% had used traditional medicine to treat common illnesses like malaria and typhoid fevers. While students in social sciences expressed belief in its efficacy and supported integration into the health system, students in biological sciences emphasized the need for more research and

regulation.¹⁶ Family and peer networks also play a major role in promoting traditional medicine use. In Lagos, social endorsement, especially from friends and relatives, was a strong motivator, even in cases where side effects were experienced.¹⁷ With technological advancement, promotion has expanded through radio, loudspeakers, and social media. However, concerns about unregulated advertising have led to calls for tighter controls to prevent the spread of unsafe practices. Documentation efforts, such as the ethnobotanical study conducted in Mubi, Adamawa State, reinforce the depth of indigenous knowledge, identifying species like *Neolamarckia cadamba* for cancer treatment.¹⁸ A study also highlighted the holistic role traditional medicine plays in managing chronic conditions like diabetes and hypertension, while underscoring the need for standardization and stronger regulation.¹⁹

Despite widespread use, gaps remain in understanding traditional medicine practices among specific populations. While middle-income earners and those with primary education have higher usage rates, the reasons behind these patterns need further exploration. Moreover, how the availability of effective certified medicines influences these practices is under-researched, as is the question of how traditional remedies can be safely integrated into Nigeria's formal healthcare system.²⁰ Against this backdrop, this study aimed to explore the use of traditional medicine for treating illnesses in children in Karu, a semi-urban area in Nasarawa State, North Central Nigeria. The specific objectives were to understand community perceptions, identify types of traditional remedies used, and explore the factors that influence caregivers' decisions to use traditional medicine for children. This localized study was expected to provide insights that would contribute to public health strategies and the broader discourse on traditional medicine in Nigeria.

Methodology

Study area

This study was conducted in Karu Local Government Area, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Karu is a semi-urban area with an estimated population of 291,900 residents spread across 2,640 km² of land mass. The area has experienced over 70% population growth in the past 16 years, largely due

to its proximity to Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. The population is primarily composed of middle-to lower-income individuals, including civil servants, small business owners, and private sector employees, particularly those working in Abuja's Central District. Karu is characterized by unstructured settlement patterns and poor waste management, contributing to a high prevalence of infectious diseases such as malaria, typhoid, and cholera, especially among children.²¹

Study population

The study targeted women residing in Karu who served as primary caregivers or mothers of children under five years of age. These participants were chosen because they are typically responsible for managing the health of young children, especially when they fall ill. Given their close interactions with children, these women were well-positioned to provide meaningful insights into health-seeking behaviour, particularly the use of traditional medicine.

Study design

A cross sectional research design was employed through which qualitative data was collected using in-depth interviews (IDIs). Participants were interviewed using a semi-structured guide, with interviews conducted in either English or Hausa, depending on participant preference. All interviews were audio-recorded with the consent of participants, translated where necessary, and transcribed verbatim.

Sampling method

Purposive sampling was used to recruit participants from community gathering locations, such as local markets and women's meeting venues. Caregivers of children under five were approached and invited to participate. Those who expressed interest completed a brief screening questionnaire to determine prior experience with traditional medicine in managing childhood illnesses.

“Prior experience with traditional medicine” was operationalized as having either (i) administered herbal remedies, (ii) consulted a traditional healer, or (iii) used non-orthodox practices for a child under five within the past 12 months. The

screening tool consisted of three questions, including:

1. “Have you ever used herbs, roots, or other traditional remedies for your child when they were sick?”
2. “Have you taken your child to a traditional healer in the past 12 months?”
3. “If yes, can you briefly describe the illness and the treatment provided?”

Only caregivers answering “yes” to at least one of these questions were selected for in-depth interviews.

Sampling saturation

Recruitment was guided by the principle of **thematic saturation**. After the 11th interview, responses began to repeat previously identified themes such as preference for herbs for fever management, reliance on mothers-in-law for treatment decisions, and barriers to accessing formal healthcare. Two additional interviews were conducted to confirm saturation. By the 13th interview, no new codes or ideas emerged, and data redundancy was evident. Although the sample size is not statistically representative of all women in Karu, the objective of this qualitative study was not generalizability but rather depth of understanding. The narratives of the 13 participants provided sufficient richness to address the research objectives.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze participants' demographic characteristics using SPSS version 24. For the qualitative data, the interviews were transcribed verbatim and a deductive coding approach applied, guided by domains in the interview guide (e.g reasons for using traditional medicine, sources of knowledge, perceived effectiveness, barriers to formal care). Transcripts were manually coded on printed copies by the researchers.

To enhance reliability, a second reviewer independently coded two randomly selected transcripts, and discrepancies were discussed and resolved, resulting in minor refinements to the coding framework. A third-party reviewer, who was not involved in data collection, cross-checked the final coded data against the raw transcripts to ensure accuracy and credibility. Themes were identified by grouping similar codes into broader

categories, then refined iteratively through constant comparison across transcripts.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Bingham University Teaching Hospital Ethics Committee (NHREC/21/05/2005/00935). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the research process.

Results

A total of thirteen mothers/caregivers of children aged 0–5 years participated in the study.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of caregivers of under-five children in Karu, Nigeria

Variable	Frequency n = 13	Percentage %
Age (Years)		
<30	6	46.2
>30	7	53.8
Sources of income		
Trading	6	46.2
Farming	2	15.4
Employed	3	23.1
Spouse	2	15.4
Educational level		
Primary	2	15.4
Secondary	4	30.8
Post-secondary	6	46.2
Higher Degree	1	7.7
Economic status		
Low	3	23.1
Middle	8	61.5
High	2	15.4

From Table 1, majority of the 13 research participants (53.8%) were 30 years and above (mean=29.6 years, SD=5.0). A large number of the participants (46.2%) were operating small personal businesses, while 23.1% were working with the government. Only 7.7% of the participants had an advanced degree, while 46.2% had completed post-secondary school education. Most of the participants were middle-income earners with a monthly income between ₦75,000 and ₦100,000, based on Renaissance Capital (2011) threshold.

Behaviour towards usage of traditional medicine

Caregivers' and mothers' behaviour regarding the use of traditional medicine vary depending on the

type of medicine chosen, the age of the child, the dosage, the method of administration, and the conditions being treated.

“Before I administer any traditional medicine to my child orally, I do taste it first in my mouth, once it is bitter, I don't give it to my child because that may result in a liver problem. I also do try to know the ingredients of the traditional medicine I give my children, especially in situations when I buy it already prepared. After knowing the ingredients, I go online to read about such ingredients before giving my child, I am aware that some of the traditional medicine have significant side effects as such I am always careful how I use it”. (Civil Servant, 28 years)

Regarding the age at which traditional medicine

should be administered to children, respondents' opinions varied. While some felt it should not be administered to children under the age of one year, others believed it could. The majority of respondents stated that they treated fever and jedi-jedi with traditional medicine for their children under one year of age.

“When my daughter had jedi-jedi, I didn't give her the medication directly, I was the one that drank the traditional medicine hoping that she will suck via breast milk. However, I bathed her with the medicine to heal the rashes on her body which is one of the symptoms of jedi-jedi. I was afraid of giving her traditional medicine to drink at such a tender age” (Trader, 30 years)

Regarding the kinds of illnesses they seek to treat with traditional medicine, some parents utilized traditional medicine for a wide range of childhood ailments, while others limited its use to specific conditions.

“For me, any ailments that have an efficient hospital treatment like malaria I don't use traditional medicine but for ailments like jedi-jedi that sometimes don't respond to clinical medicines I use traditional medicine”. (Civil Servant, 29 years)

“I am well knowledgeable about traditional medicine; I grew up using traditional medicine which I learnt from my grandmother. I have no reservation concerning using traditional medicine nor the age I use it for my children. I use traditional medicine to treat all kinds of ailments for my children. I know how to mix them from natural herbs and leaves by myself”. (Housewife, 33 years)

Common childhood ailments treated with traditional medicine

The kind of children's ailments being treated with traditional medicine differ relative to user's (mothers/care givers of children) culture, background, common ailments in the community, and their understanding of the efficacy of the traditional medicines.⁸

A common ailment identified from the data is a condition known locally as "Jedi-jedi." Despite the lack of standardized clinical signs for diagnosis of jedi-jedi, traditional medicine practitioners describe jedi-jedi based on their personal experiences of the disease. It is often

referred to as an anal tear (anal fissure) or a pile, sometimes known as hemorrhoids. It is a peri-anal irritation that is known as anal pruritus. Some refer to it as diaper rash, amoebiasis, or intestinal candidiasis. People's perceptions of jedi-jedi differ, so do the approaches taken by traditional medicine practitioners in treating it. Jedi-jedi is frequently observed in infants 0–1 year old.

“I currently have three children, for all my children I used traditional medicine to treat their jedi-jedi especially when they are between the ages of 3 months to 18 months. Jedi-jedi becomes worse for children when they start teething. Though I do use clinical medicine to treat it sometimes, most times it is not effective hence I still have to rely on traditional medicine. The traditional medicine I use includes a combination of moringa, mango, neem tree, guava, and orange/lemon leaves. This has been very effective in treating jedi-jedi for my children”. (Trader, 35 years)

Fever is a prevalent condition among childhood ailments being treated with traditional medicine. The mixture of traditional medicine being used for treatment of fever also varies from person to person. Participants reported teething as one of the conditions where they often use traditional medicine. The use of powdered substances on gums of children to ease teething is also a common practice among the participants. Skin rashes and dry skin are also common ailments for which treatment traditional medicine is used. Participants reported using powdered and oily forms of traditional medicine for treatment of skin conditions. Such substances are often scrubbed on the skin surface to facilitate the healing process.

Diarrhea often related with jedi-jedi is also a common ailment being treated with traditional medicine for children ages 0-5 years. Treatment for diarrhea also differs from person to person depending on their experience and availability for the traditional medicine supplements. There was no standardized or uniform formula for preparation of traditional medicine used in treatment of diarrhea by the respondents. Also, methods of use vary from person to person. Some respondents reported administering oral solution to treat diarrhea while others reported administration of anal solutions. For some

respondents there is no clear difference between jedi-jedi and diarrhea as jedi-jedi is often accompanied with diarrhea while some diarrhea can occur even without jedi-jedi.

“The common ailments my children suffer from that I often rely on use of traditional medicine are fever, diarrhea and jedi-jedi. The three of them can occur at the same time espically when my children are teething. I do see signs of jedi-jedi on their anus which is often accompanied by diarrhea and at the same time fever that is often related with weakness of the body and increasing body temperature. In such situations I usually mix different kinds of leaves and roots to prepare the medicine because most of the leaves can be used for different purposes”. (Housewife, age 37)

Forms of traditional medicine

Traditional medications are given to children orally in the form of liquids often found in already prepared solutions or sometimes prepared from a combination of different leaves, roots, vegetables, herbs, flowers, seeds, or bark of trees. They can be found in powdered form commonly used for treatment of open wounds and skin conditions. Traditional medicines can also be found in oil forms. Oil forms of traditional medicine are commonly used for treatment of skin condition. Some respondents reported using oil for treatment of jedi-jedi.

“For all my four children, I have used oil extracts from the seeds of African mahogany tree, the bitter taste of oil is very effective in treatment of jedi-jedi because it neutralizes the sweets that the baby gets from the mother through the breast milk”. (Civil servant, 34 years)

Solid forms of traditional medicine are used in varied ways for children. They can be burnt to produce smoke for sick children to inhale for treatment purposes. This practice is common among the Hausa and Fulani in northern Nigeria. It is commonly called “Hayaki” and recognized as a spiritual method of traditional medicine.

“Hayaki is a traditional remedy I inherited from my parents; it is part of our culture that I cannot do without regardless of the kind of clinical medicines available because hayaki provides

spiritual healing to children. Some ailments are not medically caused as such no matter the kind of clinical medicine you use it won't provide any result, in such instances hayaki is significant” (Housewife, 22 years)

Traditional medicines are commonly used for children aged 0 to 5 years old as children within that age group are usually exposed to many kinds of illness because of their relatively low immune system that makes them extremely vulnerable.

“When my child had measles, my mother gave me a combination of herbs to cook and bathe my child. I followed her instruction, and for one week I bathed my child with the mixture and my child got healed”. (Trader, 23 years)

Source of information

Most of the respondents reported getting information about traditional medicines from their grandparents, parents, friends, neighbours, and traditional healers.

I learnt about different traditional medicines and how to mix them from my grandmother. I have been an advocate and promoter of traditional medicine to my friends because this is what I grew up using. When I see a child suffering from an ailment like Jedi-jedi I quickly recommend traditional mixture to the parents because I believe in its effectiveness” (Civil Servant, 29 years)

With increasing access to technology and access to the internet, advertisements of traditional medicine has been on the increase hence increasing access to information about traditional medicine. Traditional medicine sellers now advertise their products and services online and on social media platforms. It is also a common practice in Karu for traditional medicine sellers to advertise their products in public places like markets and parks through the use of devices like speakers and microphones. This practice is shifting the use of traditional medicine from something that has cultural attachment to something that is now mainstream.

Diagnosis

Prior to employing traditional medicine as a

therapeutic approach, the diagnosis of a condition is made utilizing experience or intuition.²² Prior to beginning treatment, the etiology of the illness is typically not ascertained through clinical or laboratory testing. Traditional medicine non-users have questioned and critiqued this strategy. On the other hand, proponents of traditional medicine have contended that they treat illnesses with these remedies because they are familiar with the symptoms and indicators of those conditions. Before choosing which traditional medicine to take, several respondents said kids should be tested. According to a 28 year old trader, doing so will guarantee the medication's efficacy.

“Several illnesses have similar symptoms, administering traditional medicine to a child without knowing what the cause of the illness is, is dangerous. I have been using traditional medicine for my children but after ensuring that they are tested first. Research Participant (Trader, 28 years old)

Dosage

Since traditional medicines are most times made or prepared by the people who use them, there is no set dosage or quantity that is prescribed to be given to children.²³ Mothers decide how much to give their kids at each usage based on their own discretion. When conditions worsen, most users said they increased the dosage and concentration of the traditional blend to hasten healing.

“There is no descriptive measurement or dosage for traditional medicine, even if you buy already prepared one there is no specific dosage for administration. Most times I rely on my experience and advice from people to determine dosage. Some of the medicines are taken by both the mother and the child so that the child can suck via breast milk. When the ailment is severe, I usually administer a higher dosage, I stop giving the child as soon I see healing taking place” (Housewife, 23 years)

Factors influencing the use of traditional medicine

Several factors influence the use of traditional medicine for different users. The factors however cross match each other as what most respondents consider to be important is to see recovery in their children regardless of the kind of medication used.

“Personally, what I consider most important when my child is sick is for the child to be healed and be strong. Whether is clinical medicine or traditional medicine is used, what is most important is the result. I believe it is the same with every parent, when a child is sick, we as parents become restless. In that restlessness whatever will solve the problem is what we go for” (Housewife, 23 years)

The factors that influence the use of traditional medicine by mothers for their children include:

Availability

Majority of traditional medicines are made from readily available plant and animal extracts. Certain traditional medicines can be found in already prepared solutions made by traditional healers. The availability of plants and animal extracts for preparation and people's knowledge of how to mix them makes traditional medicine a widely accepted and practiced behaviour among mothers in Karu Nasarawa State Nigeria.

“I prepare the traditional medicines I use for my children from trees and plants around me, any traditional medicine that I don't prepare myself I don't give to my children. I grew up in the village where I learnt these remedies because we had no access to hospitals. Some of the leaves I use in preparing my traditional medicine are only found in my village and I don't know their names in English”. (Civil Servant, 29 years)

Effectiveness

According to the responses gathered from research participants, one of the main reasons mothers continue to use traditional medicine for the treatment of illnesses in children is its effectiveness. All of the participants mentioned using traditional medicine to treat certain conditions, such as jedi-jedi, and mentioned how more successful traditional medicine has been than clinical medicines.

“I used traditional medicine to treat jedi-jedi for all my five children. The truth is clinical medicines are not effective in treating jedi-jedi. It seems scientists are yet to discover the cure for jedi-jedi because almost all my friends used traditional medicine to treat jedi-jedi for children. Some children don't suffer from jedi-jedi, in rare situations some children respond positively to nystatin when used for the treatment of jedi-jedi but it has never worked for any of my children” (Civil servant, 34 years)

In the treatment of fever, respondents have expressed the effectiveness of mixtures like neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*) and mango tree (*Mangifera Indica*) for treatment. They expressed that some children develop resistance to clinical medicines as such traditional medicines become the most effective method for treatment.

“When my daughter was 3 years old, she suffered from severe fever. We went to several hospitals including Jankwano in Jos. We tried several things, but nothing worked. Finally, I was recommended to use traditional medicine which I did and since then my child did not experience that kind of severe fever” (Trader, 35 years)

“I am enrolled in the national health insurance scheme as such I do have access to somewhat free medical services and medication. However, I prefer traditional medicines for the treatment of some ailments in my children. The reason is that I have tested and can testify that those traditional medicines are more effective than the clinical medicines, even some doctors recognize this fact” (Civil servant, 34 years)

Affordability

When people prepare their own traditional medicine, the components needed to make it are readily available and can be obtained for a very little amount of money. Clinical medicines are more priced than traditional medicines as such people are motivated to go for traditional medicines.

“I was introduced to using traditional medicine for my son when I was in the university by my nanny. At that time, I didn't have enough money to be buying clinical medicine so I accepted the idea of

using traditional medicine for my son. As a student, I could afford traditional medicine without much stress. I was lucky my baby didn't suffer many childhood ailments aside from jedi-jedi and sometimes weakness of the body because of teething” (House-wife, 25 years)

Time of healing and recovery

According to the respondents, traditional medicine treats children's illnesses more quickly than clinical treatments. They argued that traditional medicines contain higher concentrations of active ingredients, whereas clinical medicines are sometimes diluted, containing only small amounts of active ingredients. This suggests that traditional medicine may be more effective in a shorter period of time. Additionally, the respondents claimed that traditional medicines, often used fresh after being obtained, are more effective than clinical medicines, which may lose potency due to long-term storage from production to pharmaceutical shelves.

“Any clinical medicine prescribed for a child has to be used at least for a week, some medications like nystatin for jedi-jedi have to be used continuously unlike traditional medicine that provides relief and healing for a child within days. I tried using nystatin to treat jedi-jedi for my first child, I used it for more than three months but noticed no significant change. I was then recommended to use the already made jedi-jedi traditional medicine that is commonly sold in stores and some pharmacists and within seven days I started noticing results. Since then, I have been using traditional medicine to treat jedi-jedi for my remaining two children without even trying nystatin on them” (Housewife, 23 years)

Ineffective health system

One reason why some women choose to treat their children's illnesses with traditional medication is because of the stress involved and the time they often spent in hospitals receiving medical care. Based on the data gathered from the respondents, receiving medical services in public hospitals and primary health care centers in Karu is typically stressful and time-consuming, while using private clinics for prompt and efficient services is very expensive hence going for the option of traditional

medicine.

Discussion

Previous studies have shown that concerns about potential adverse effects discourage many individuals from using traditional medicine for treating childhood illnesses.²⁴ However, this study explored respondents' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding traditional medicine—including its perceived effectiveness and risks—and found that usage is widespread across socioeconomic classes, and not limited to low-income groups as commonly assumed. The increasing acceptance of traditional medicine in Nigeria appears to be driven largely by its perceived effectiveness, especially for conditions like *jedi-jedi* in children.^{12,15}

Rather than being a consequence of limited access to biomedical care, the use of traditional remedies is often motivated by perceived efficacy, cultural familiarity, and local availability of medicinal ingredients.^{12,14} This study observed that the specific formulations of traditional medicine vary widely, influenced by the plants, animal products, and minerals accessible within a given community. For instance, while neem leaves (*Azadirachta indica*) were frequently cited as an ingredient for treating fever and *jedi-jedi*, their application varied from one respondent to another. This variability made it difficult to identify neem or any other ingredient as a consistent active component or to establish standardized treatments across the study population.

Many participants were either unaware of or unconcerned about the potential side effects of traditional medicines. Dosages were often estimated by caregivers, and remedies typically lacked labeling or ingredient lists—especially when purchased rather than homemade—posing risks such as overdose or organ toxicity. Nevertheless, a prevailing belief was that natural substances are inherently safe, and that freshness enhances both safety and efficacy. This perception reinforces continued use, even when clinically approved alternatives are available.

One participant reflected this sentiment thus:

“I am currently being careful of using excessive clinical medicine for my children because it can accumulate in their organs to create a bigger problem. As a young girl growing up, I was exposed to a lot of antibiotics because I was consistently ill. This led to the accumulation of

these medications in my body which resulted in kidney stones. I had to undergo surgery to remove the stones. I don't want my children to pass through this kind of experience. Most times I rely on traditional medicine because they are made from natural substances with little or no side effects.” — 30-year-old trader

Despite its widespread use, traditional medicine in Nigeria remains largely unregulated. Many of the remedies sold in public spaces such as markets and motor parks are not certified by the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) and often lack essential labeling, including manufacturing or expiration dates.²³ Although the Lagos State Government has introduced a code of conduct for traditional medicine practitioners, similar national-level initiatives remain limited, and enforcement remains a challenge.

Traditional medicine continues to be promoted mainly through word-of-mouth and community trust rather than formal advertising. Study participants stressed the need to educate the public about traditional remedies, especially for childhood ailments perceived as poorly managed by conventional medicine. Interestingly, while no respondents called for standardization of traditional medicine, many emphasized the need for government investment in its development and broader promotion. They viewed traditional remedies as safer and more effective for specific conditions, reinforcing a strong preference for their use. This view resonates with findings that documented the use of traditional medicine in cancer treatment in Mubi, Adamawa State.¹⁸

Nevertheless, this study has some limitations that warrant consideration. Participants were recruited purposively from community gathering places, and only those who expressed interest and reported prior use of traditional medicine were included. This approach may have introduced selection bias, as caregivers who are more open, available, or with positive experiences of traditional medicine may have been more likely to participate. Conversely, those with negative experiences, concerns about stigma, or competing time demands may have declined participation, and their perspectives were therefore not captured. In addition, the small sample size and focus on a single semi-urban setting limit the generalizability

of findings to other regions of Nigeria. However, as with most qualitative studies, the aim was not statistical representativeness but to generate rich, in-depth insights into caregivers' beliefs and practices. Despite these limitations, the findings provide valuable context for understanding how cultural beliefs, perceived efficacy, and community trust shape health-seeking behaviour in childhood illness management.

The findings highlight an urgent need for context-sensitive health education that addresses both the benefits and risks of traditional medicine use for childhood illnesses. Health promotion programs should not dismiss traditional practices but instead build on existing community trust to encourage safe, evidence-based practices. Regulatory agencies such as NAFDAC need to strengthen oversight of herbal products, ensuring proper labelling and safety monitoring. Furthermore, integrating traditional medicine practitioners into community health dialogues may improve collaboration, reduce misinformation, and support safer treatment options for children. By recognizing traditional medicine as a significant component of local health-seeking behaviour, policy makers can design more inclusive interventions that bridge the gap between cultural practices and biomedical care.

Conclusion

The findings show that the use of traditional medicine is rooted in longstanding cultural practices, and it remains prevalent despite the widespread availability of clinically tested pharmaceuticals and advancements in modern healthcare. Importantly, its use is not confined to rural or low-income populations which challenges the common assumption that traditional medicine is used primarily due to limited access to clinical care.

There is an urgent need for government investment in scientific research to evaluate the safety and efficacy of widely used traditional remedies. Such efforts could inform standardization, regulation, and possible integration of validated treatments into the national healthcare system, ultimately ensuring safer and more inclusive healthcare options for all.

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